

Integrans and their role antibiotic resistance

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Introduction

- **Hall** and **Colli** first report in **1989**
- The genetic elements are movable plasmids, chromosomes and transposons that carry resistive genes while they are inside the genetic cassettes.
- Horizontal transmission of integrons is considered to be the most successful way of releasing resistance genes and the emergence of multi-resistance species (**MDRs**).

Types of integron

Super Integrons

- Located on the long arm of the chromosome and carries a genetic cassette with different actions

Integrons resistance

- Resistance gene cassettes against antibiotics and Dezenfektan to carry and can be placed on chromosome or plasmid.

- An integron is generally **defined** by the presence of an integrase gene (*intI*) and a proximal primary recombination site (*attI*)
- The amino acid sequences of **IntI** integrases have been used as a basis for **dividing** integrons into classes with those carrying
- *intI1* defined as class 1
- *intI2* as class 2
- *intI3* as class 3

Classification

- From the differences and divergence in the **sequences of *intI*, integrons** have been classified and **divided** into several classes. Up to date, 4 general classes of integrons have been identified and distinguished, termed classes 1–4 integrons
- classes 1–3 integrons are capable of **acquiring** same gene cassettes via similar **recombination platform**
- **class 1 integron**, with focus on **Gram-negative** microorganisms.

class 4 integron was firstly identified on the small chromosome of *Vibrio cholerae* and found to be an integral component of many **γ -proteobacterial** genomes

Structure

- All integrons consist of three main components, including the 5' end of the protected area and the end of the 3', and a central variable region of 3' and 5' is formed.
- **area 5'** Include:
 - 1- Inti
 - 2- att
 - 3- Pc,P2
 - 4- Pint
- **3' area** Integrons have three different structures that are different classes of Integrons

Integron structure

Gene cassettes

- cassettes located within the **variable region** of integrons
- gene cassettes are integrated between two recombination sites (*attI* and *attC*) and thus become part of the integron
- gene cassettes are generally found to be **lack of promoters**
- most cassettes encode resistance against antibiotics cover a wide range of antibiotics, with up to date more than 130 distinct antibiotic resistance genes characterized via unique *attC* sites.
- most **classes of antibiotics** containing all known
- β -lactams, aminoglycosides, Chloramphenicol, streptothricin, trimethoprim, rifampin, erythromycin, quinolones, Fosfomycin, lincomycin
- and **antiseptics of the quaternary ammonium-compound** family

attC sites

The integrons recombination site is known as the **Element 59bp**, which is bounded by these repeat sequences of the genetic cassettes.

5' Conserved Segment

3' segment

Structure of multiresistant integrons (MRI)

Mobility

- with mobile DNA elements (transposons or plasmids)

Class 1 integron

- Integrons have been found in approximately **9 % of the sequenced bacterial genomes**, and class 1 integron platform is the most ubiquitous and has been the most commonly reported among **clinical bacteria**
- Considered to be directly linked with **Tn402**-like transposons and associated with **Tn3 transposon** family
- this class of integron is capable of capturing gene cassettes via this site-specific recombination platform, and gene cassettes are also able to be further expressed from a common promoter located in the 5'-conserved segment (5'-CS)

Structure entegron1

Fig. 1

Schematic representation of a class 1 integron. *P1* promoter for transcription of gene cassettes, *P2* second promoter that is usually inactive, *int* integrase gene, *attI* integration site, *qacE* partially deleted gene that encodes quaternary ammonium compound resistance, *sul1* sulphonamide resistance, *orf5* unknown function, *P* promoters of the *qacEΔ* and *sul1* genes, *attC* sequence on the gene cassette recognized by the integrase

Fig. 3

Integration and excision of gene cassettes by site-specific recombination. *IntI* encoded by the *intI* gene in the integron catalyses recombination between the *attI* site of the integron and/or the *attC* site(s) of gene cassette(s) resulting in insertion or excision of a cassette. One or more noncassette resistance genes may be inserted at the position of the 3'-CS. *Horizontal arrows* indicate the opposite orientations of *intI* and cassette-borne genes

Occurrence and prevalence of class 1 integron in Gram-negative microorganisms

Date	Bacterial	Occurrence of class 1 integron and the array of gene cassettes	Sampling
2006	<i>Shigella</i>	<i>EstX-aadA1</i> (3.85 %, 1/26)	Hiroshima prefecture, Japan; 2000–2004
2002	<i>Salmonella</i>	36.2 % (34/94); <i>aadA2-bla (PSE-1)</i> (61.76 % 21/34); <i>aadA1-aadA2-bla (PSE-1)</i> (38.23 %, 13/34)	Animals, Japan
2000	<i>V. cholerae</i>	44/176; <i>aadB-aadA2-blaP1-dfrA1-dfrA15</i>	Thailand
2002	<i>Burkholderia</i>	29.4 % (5/17); <i>oxa-aac (6'-1a)</i>	Ireland
2004	<i>Campylobacter</i>	62/378	Ireland
2008	<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>	50/226	Addenbrooke's Hospital
2005	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	4/32 (12.5 %); <i>sat-1-aadA</i>	Meat and meat products, Norway
2008	<i>E. coli</i>	59.5 % (355/597)	South Thailand
2011	<i>E. coli</i>		Preliminary study in Guangzhou, China
2009	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	45.8 % (54/118)	Preliminary study in Guangzhou, China
2008	<i>Serratia</i>	1/30; <i>aacC1-ORFX-ORFY-aadA1</i>	Canada

Occurrence and prevalence of class 1 integron in Gram-positive microorganisms

Date	Bacterial	History	Description
1998	<i>Corynebacterium glutamicum</i>	First class 1 integron evidence in G ⁺ microorganisms	InCg on pCG4 (29-kb), identical to InC on pSA1700
1999	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	First class 1 integron report within <i>Enterococcus</i> and the species of <i>E. faecalis</i>	<i>aadA</i> was found via horizontal transfer between <i>E. faecalis</i>
2002	<i>Corynebacterium glutamicum</i>		On pTET-3 (27.8-kb), with a novel <i>aadA9</i> detected
2001– 2004	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> <i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	First class 2 integron evidence in G ⁺ microorganisms and first report of class 1 integron on the species of <i>E. Faecium</i>	Three arrays (<i>dfrA12-orfF-aadA2</i> , <i>dfrA17-aadA5</i> and <i>aadA2</i>) for class 1 integron and array <i>dfrA1-sat1-aadA1</i> for class 2 integron
2001– 2002	<i>Streptococcus</i>	First class 1 integron report within <i>Streptococcus</i>	Array of <i>dfrA12-orfF-aadA2</i> detected
2004	<i>Corynebacterium ammoniagenes</i> <i>Corynebacterium casei</i> <i>Corynebacterium glutamicum</i> <i>Aerococcus</i>	First class 1 integron report on <i>Aerococcus</i> spp. and the species of, <i>C. ammoniagenes</i> , <i>C. casei</i> , <i>Brevibacterium thiogenitalis</i> ; also the first identification of class 1 integron from environmental G ⁺ microorganisms	Such integrons carried various antibiotic resistance genes and may serve as the potentially large reservoir of class 1 integron

Occurrence and prevalence of class 1 integron in Gram-positive microorganisms

	<i>Aerococcus</i>		
	<i>Brevibacterium</i>		
	<i>thiogenitalis</i>		
	<i>Staphylococcus</i>		
2001–2006	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	First class 1 integron evidence from clinical G ⁺ microorganisms from a large scale and a long study duration; first class 1 integron identification from clinical <i>S. aureus</i> and the species of <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>S. haemolyticus</i> , <i>S. hominis</i> and <i>S. warneri</i>	Typically class 1 integrons were observed, with <i>intI1</i> and 3'CS of $\Delta qacE$, a <i>sulI</i> gene and ORF5. Four arrays (<i>dfrA12-orfF-aadA2</i> , <i>dfrA17-aadA5</i> , <i>aacA4-cmlA1</i> and <i>aadA2</i>) detected [3]
	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>		
	<i>Staphylococcus haemolyticus</i>		
	<i>Staphylococcus hominis</i>		
	<i>Staphylococcus warneri</i>		
2009	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>		With 78 % homologous <i>intI1</i> and the cassette arrays of <i>aac6</i> [45]
2013	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	First class 1 integron report on the species of <i>S. saprophyticus</i>	With identification rate of class 1 integron as 40.5 % (81/200) [46]
	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>		
	<i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i>		

Class 2 integron

- class 2 integron is commonly found to be associated with the **Tn7** transposon family (Tn7 and its derivatives, such as Tn1825, Tn1826 and Tn4132)
- The homology of amino-acid sequences of a typical *intI2* gene are found to be less than 50 % comparing to the *intI1*, and unfunctional due to the replacement of the internal termination codon with **glutamic acid** (amino acid 179) and thus the production of a shorter and inactive polypeptide which was unable to catalyse the recombination reaction
- High prevalence in gram-negative bacteria, including **,Acinetobacter ,Shigella, Salmonella.**
- The genetic cassettes in this class are related to resistance to **trimethoprim, streptomycin and spectinomycin.**

- **3` end structure**
- **tni**
- **Res**
- **orfs 9**

Class 3 integron

- *Arakawa* was first discovered in Japan in 1996.
- Rarely, there are clinical specimens, but recently *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Pseudomonas putida* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* have been found in Japan, Portugal and Canada.
- end 3' is similar to Integron Class 1 Included:
- qacEΔ1
- sul1
- orf 5,6
- The only difference with class 1 integrin is in the absence of *transposing* genes.
- Several genetic casts included:
- bla Imp-1
- aacA4

Class 4 integron

- The word Super Integron was first named by Mazel et al. In 1998. In fact Integrons Class IV are the same Super Integrons
- *Vibrio cholerae*
- The size of these large and is about 126Kb and has at least 178 cassettes of genes
- Some of them are related to aminoglycoside-phosphotransferase, toxins, RNA-methyltransferase, DNA glycolase, and unlike the three previous superintegron gene cassettes, they do not code for any antibiotic resistance, and are more likely to be associated with genomic evolution, such as the metabolism of DNA changes and Adaptive functions
- gene cassettes imparting resistance to the antibiotics chloramphenicol and fosfomycin
- They do not have the ability to move, and they are not associated with any of the moving genetic elements.
- *Vibrionaceae, Shewanella, Xanthomonas, Pseudomonad*
- And other bacteria from the beta-protobacter group that are present in peripheral samples and non-pathogens have been observed, and are not exclusive to vibrio cholera.

Integrans and beta-lactamase enzymes

- **Integrans cassettes** in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* and Enterobacteriaceae species exists and contains the **beta-lactamase enzymes Groups A, B, D** Ambler is classified.
- eight families of beta-lactamase enzymes have been isolated from different sites in the structure of **the III and I integrans**, including the family VEB, GES, IBC, CTX-M, PSE, IMP, OXA, and VIM enzymes.

β -Lactamase	Host species	Origin
VEB-1	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Vietnam
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Vietnam
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	France
	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	Thailand
VEB-1a	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Kuwait
VEB-1b	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Kuwait
VEB-2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Thailand
GES-1	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	French Guiana
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	France
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ^a	Portugal
GES-2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	South Africa
IBC-1	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	Greece
IBC-2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Greece
CTX-M-2	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	Argentina
	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	Argentina
CTX-M-9	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Spain
PSE-1	<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	Thailand

- β -lactamase A in class I integrams in different species of gram-negative bacteria
- a: type that has Class 3 integrons.

β -Lactamase	Host species	Origin
IMP-1	<i>Serratia marcescens</i> ^a	Japan
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Japan
IMP-2	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Italy
IMP-3	<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	Japan
IMP-4	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Hong Kong
	<i>Citrobacter youngae</i>	China
IMP-6	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Japan
IMP-7	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Canada
IMP-8	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Taiwan
IMP-12	<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>	Italy
VIM-1	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Italy
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Italy
	<i>Achromobacter xylosoxydans</i>	Italy
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Greece
VIM-2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	France
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Italy
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Spain

- β -lactamases B in class I integrons in different species of gram-negative bacteria
- a: type that has Class 3 integrons.

β -Lactamase	Host species	Origin
OXA-1	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	Italy
OXA-5	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	South Africa
OXA-9	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	France
OXA-10	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Vietnam
OXA-11	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Turkey
OXA-14	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Turkey
OXA-16	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Turkey
OXA-19	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	France
OXA-20	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	France
OXA-28	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	France
OXA-30	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	France

- β -lactamases D present in class 1 introns in different species of gram-negative bacteria

3	2	1	origin	bacteria
0	31%	97%	hamedan	Acinetobacter baumannii
3	44	100	shahrekord	Acinetobacter baumannii
	0	6.35	Tehran	pseudomonas aeruginosa
	14	58	Tehran	Acinetobacter baumannii
4	5.14	95	kerman	salmonella enteritidis
		58	Tehran Gazvin	pseudomonas aeruginosa

conclusion

- **Horizontal transfer** of resistance genes are considered to be the major cause to **facilitate the rapid spread of antibiotic resistance in microbes.**
- integrons **play core role in antibiotic resistance** of microorganisms and have been shown to contribute to the wide spread and distribution of antibiotic resistant genes among bacteria
- **identification** of integrons **distribution** and spread of integrons and **cassettes** arrays, as well as the role of such integrons play in the dissemination and spread of antimicrobial resistance, **require further investigation.**

**Thank you for your
attention!!**